

LINGUISTIC TERMS RELATED TO PROFESSIONALISM.

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Annotation: The article deals with implementation of cognitive-communicative approach to foreign language education of non-linguistic students. In this connection, we should take into consideration the speaker's speech strategy in the attempt to achieve maximum communication efficiency. The recognition of the role of context in a foreign professional discourse emphasizes the great importance of pragmatic procedures for its analysis and its cognitive aspects. This fact should be taken into account in the process of teaching foreign language professional discourse. The criteria for its formation are defined as proficiency in the mental professional lexicon.

Key words: linguoculturology, linguocultureme, intertextuality, words realia, conceptual world picture, professionalism

Technical terms are an essential part of technical and scientific writing. Each field or specialty typically uses the vocabulary that relays a variety of specialized concepts by means of technical language. These special terms convey concentrated meanings that have been built up over significant periods of study of a field. The value of a specialized set of terms lies in the way each term condenses a mass of information into a single word. Technical terminology is often thought of as shorthand, a way of gaining great depth and accuracy of meaning with economy of words. Technical terms often blend readily into formulae and mathematical manipulation, a term such as force being folded into a formula such as $f = ma$. This quantification allows the concept to be manipulated mathematically.

Professionalism is a seemingly vague term that you've never given much thought to in the past. But now that you're getting closer to launching a professional career, however, this word has taken on a lot more significance. You're about to be on the hunt for a new job in your career field, and you're aware that professionalism is a trait managers will be looking for in your interviews.

You know that professionalism matters, but you still have some questions about this characteristic. Why is professionalism important, and what can you do to be more professional?

We spoke with HR specialists and hiring managers to get the answers you're looking for. These experts are sharing their experiences from the opposite side of the interview table, with insights on the importance of professionalism and how to act in a professional manner as you enter the workforce.

What is professionalism?

Simply put, professionalism is the way you conduct yourself at work to represent both yourself and your company in a positive way. It includes standards for behavior that might be mandated in an employee handbook, like adhering to a certain dress code, as well as traits that are harder to pin down but still valuable to being professional in the workplace.

Professionalism goes beyond a checklist of requirements. Instead, it includes "embodying the company's values and serving as a stellar representative of the company," according to Eric

Mochnacz, HR consultant at Red Clover. "Professionalism is someone's inherent ability to do what is expected of them and deliver quality work because they are driven to do so."

The importance of professionalism. The experts agree that professionalism is one of the biggest factors in your level of career success. It might sound dramatic, but it's true! This trait affects every aspect of how you do your job. A lack of professionalism can cost you a job or promotion, and it can even put you first in line for a layoff.

"Your level of professionalism can make or break your career," Walker says. "Without it, you will never be taken seriously and you may even be looked over when it comes time to be considered for a promotion."

One reason professionalism is so important is because it's an outward display of your attitude toward your job and your company. "It's a sign of loyalty, dependability and responsibility," says Nate Masterson, HR manager at Maple Holistics. "A lack of professionalism suggests a lack of respect towards an employer, which can impact your ability to land a job."

Signs of professionalism. It's clear that professionalism is important, but what are the real-life signs of professionalism employers are looking for? Our experts have shared the examples of professionalism that are sure to catch their eye.

Despite terms numbering a great quantity, they are used by fewer people and therefore are not included into the general vocabulary. As the result terms are more constant and are, to a lesser degree, subjected to any morphological or semantic changes than the vocabulary of the every-day use.

Most researchers admit that terminology is one of the main features of the scientific style, informative core of the science language.

Terms are traditionally defined as words, compound words or word-combination used in specific contexts. In order to define correctly the concepts expressed with terms it is necessary to know the field of science or technology to which this term can be referred. Each term must be considered in connection with the words around it and the context in general, because a term is a word which acquires a definite meaning according to the field of its use in a particular case. Terminological meaning of a word is usually unchangeable but it can be revealed only in the context.

Terms are combined into systems of terms (terminology systems) that can be defined as a number of terms with fixed relations between them which reflect, in their turn, the relations between concepts that these terms designate.

A term has the same functions as any word does: nominative (nomination; i.e. naming the things), significative (generalization), communicative (communication), pragmatic (a function that indicates an attitude of a speaker to the things said or written).

There are a number of terms classifications in modern linguistics. They are based on different features of a term or aspects of their study.

In the vocabulary of a scientific / technical text one can find two main categories of terms:

- terms of a certain sphere / field that have their own definition / meaning in it;
- generally scientific terminological units (including terms of interbranch sciences), for example, widely-used terms of philosophy, political science, mathematics, philology, etc.

Terms of the first category can be, in its turn, divided into three groups: normative terms (nomenclature); professional terms (professionalisms); professional jargonisms.

Normative terms, or nomenclature, are words that denote specific concepts and conform to all

norms and requirements for national and borrowed terms: absorption, accountability, flux, time constant, waste etc);

Professional terms (professionalisms) are words and word-combinations that nominate a concept but do not reveal its complete meaning, they are comprehensible mostly for professionals. Unlike nomenclature units, professional terms can be interpreted. Thus professionalisms, as the term itself signifies, are the words used in a definite trade, profession, or a name used by people connected by common interests both at work and at home. Professional words name anew already existing concepts and have the typical properties of a special code, but they do not aim at secrecy. They perform a socially useful function in communication, facilitating a quick and adequate grasp of the message. The main feature of a professionalism is its technicality. Professionalisms are special words in the non-literary layer of the English vocabulary, whereas terms are a specialised group belonging to the literary layer of words. Terms, if they are connected with a field or branch of science or technique well-known to ordinary people, are easily decoded and enter the neutral stratum of the vocabulary. Professionalisms generally remain in circulation within a certain community, as they are linked to a common occupation and social interests.

The semantic structure of the term is usually transparent and is therefore easily understood. The semantic structure of a professionalism is often dimmed by the image on which the meaning of the professionalism is based, particularly when the features of the object in question reflect the process of work, metaphorically or metonymically. Like terms, professionalisms do not allow any polysemy, they are monosemantic. Here are some professionalisms used in different spheres of activity: tin-fish (submarine), piper (a specialist who decorates pastry with the use of a cream-pipe); a midder case (a midwifery case); outer (a knockout blow). Some professionalisms, however, like certain terms, become popular and gradually lose their professional flavour;

Professional jargonisms do not require accuracy or monosemanticity. They are also figurative to a great extent and emotionally coloured; jargonisms are a periphery of terminological vocabulary which are used in speaking and are not regulated by and are often not fixed in the dictionaries. Professionalisms should not be mixed up with jargonisms. Unlike normative and professional terms, jargonisms aim at secrecy (hammer – local anesthetic, chippie – carpenter, mudslinger - calumniator, slanderer).

Specialized vocabulary is most important and most widely spread in technical texts because it is most informative.

Though when using specialized terms, it is necessary to observe the following:

- Match terminology to the ability of the audience. You may use a term with great accuracy and still not reach your audience. It is important that you be aware of your audience's level of understanding. If they are not experts in your field, you will need to substitute more general terms for your specialized terms. That means that you may not be able to write with great accuracy about your topic.
- Use terms with consistency. Be sure that you use the same term for a given item each time. If you shift from using mass to using weight in referring to the quantity of an object, if at first you call a tool a spanner and later call it a wrench, or if you shift from the Kelvin scale to Centigrade for measuring temperature, you may confuse the reader.
- Provide clear definitions or explanations of unfamiliar terms. If you are using a

specialized term that is not widely used in your audience, even if the audience is an expert one, be sure you provide a clear definition of your term.

- Use a terminology list when you are introducing a variety of new terms into your discussion. The use of a list, which is generally placed before your introduction or in an appendix, can greatly aid a reader who wants to remind himself or herself of what you mean by the term.

Terms can also be classified according to their structure. So, due to the number of components we may have:

- one-word terms, for example: switch – вимикач;
- compound terms which are combinations of stems, either written together (flywheel – маховик hotlist - перелік адрес, що слід зберегти для майбутнього; keyword – ключове слово) or through a hyphen (all-cast – суцільнозварний, self-noise – власні шуми (апаратури), to co-invent – винайти разом з кимось).
- terminological word-combinations (these terms can be of two-, three-, four- and more constituents (plate voltage change - перепад анодної напруги; very high-speed integrated circuit - інтегральна схема з надвисокою швидкодією; high voltage transmission line – лінія високовольтних передач; braking with rocket - гальмування за допомогою ракетного двигуна; light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation - квантовомеханічне посилення або генерація світла). They can be divided into: a) free word combination (load governor – регулятор потужності; атомнаелектростанція, космічнашвидкість, радіолокаційніустановки; shock wave, internal storage, residuary estate, shock lung іт.д.) in which each component is a term that can be in two-sided relationship; b) fixed word-combinations (including phraseological units) in which components taken separately may not be terms but make terms when used together: мертвавода, важкавода, радіоактивниййод, мислячийробот; dead-wood, star system, live video, etc.)

The examples given above show that terminological word-combinations have a key word that is a core of the word group and one or more left-side attributes often together with one or more right-side or prepositional attributes that specify or modify the meaning of the term.

The research was carried out in an attempt of outnumbering all types of linguoculturemes, as there has not been presented complete assemblage of culturally marked linguistic units so far. The specific types of linguoculturemes and their functions in the literary text are discussed in the following lines: 1. Linguoculturemes are mostly performed by means of words and word combinations, including non-equivalent lexicon or realia, which is represented through the nominations of clothes (a bowler hat, white gloves and a black suit of Englishmen; a kokoshnik, sarafan and valenki of Russians), meals (toast, hamburger, fish and chips, kasha, pirajki, bliny), currency (pound, pence, penny, ruble), musical instruments (guitar, violin, accordion, balalaika), holidays (Christmas, Halloween, Valentine's Day), traditions (christening, Easter, Maslenitsa) and geographical occurrences (tsunami, tornado).

2. Phraseological units are considered to be culturally specific linguistic means. According to Telia, phraseology is the mirror where the human's national and cultural identity is reflected. There is a close relationship between phraseological units and signs of culture, as a system of values are presented in the form of etalons, symbols and stereotypes in language. For example, the phraseological units such as Hobson's choice, Queen Ann is dead, Dmascus road,

the green-eyed monster, rise from ashes, the colour bar, Smithfield bargain, the battle of the books, beauty and the beast, a bed of roses, Roman holiday, John Barleycorn, the land flowing milk and honey and others are culture relevant, as they convey historical facts, social aspects, cultural values, traditions and create similar thematic domains in the language. 3. A mythologeme is another linguistic unit which carries linguocultural element within itself. A mythologeme is a linguistic unit denoting important mythological personages, situations or events transiting from one myth to another and shared by cultures throughout the world. The main source of mythologemes is myths, which are the depictions of legends about gods and heroes, stories and fables about superhuman beings taken by the preliterate society to be a true account, usually of how the world and natural phenomena, social customs came into existence. An archetype comprises the essence of a myth, which appears to be a persistent image or symbol recurring in a particular culture. Accordingly, mythologeme plays a significant role in representing the author's conceptual world picture in the text, as the author intends to refer to a famous event or situation which is represented in a new text with a particular sense. For example, the mythologemes such as –A forbidden fruit||, –Salomon's wisdom||, –Achilles' heel||, –Pandora's box||, –The tower of Babel|| are the linguistic means displaying mythological reference in the language.

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